

Creating an Introduction to a System and Accounting Procedure of Buildings

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Abstract

The legal calculations and valuation data on buildings and structures available in this article include taxes, insurance, rationalization of buildings and structures in today's market economy, attraction of investments, systematization of accounts for buildings and structures, the number of buildings and structures. , comprehensive measures for obtaining, processing, specific system and regulation and storage of complete data on the condition and quality, types of accounting in terms of quantity and quality.

Keywords: real estate market, buildings and structures, land cadastre information system, information supply, information flow, historical and cultural monuments,

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INTRODUCTION & DISCUSSION

The computer database of cadastral data on buildings and structures is formed on the basis of data entered in the cadastral register of district, city buildings and structures, and at the end of each year cadastral data are summarized and systematized quarterly in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions, Tashkent and published in the Republic of Uzbekistan [1].

Such information, as well as legal calculations and valuations of existing buildings and structures are important in today's market economy in terms of taxes, insurance, rational marketing of buildings and structures, investment attraction, legal and economic and social protection of the population. This inevitably necessitates bringing them into one system in order to create and maintain an account of buildings and structures.

Accounting for buildings and structures is a complex activity for obtaining, processing, specific system and regulation and storage of complete information on the number, condition and quality of buildings and structures, divided into types of accounting in terms of quantity and quality.

Quantitative accounting of buildings and structures includes information on their distribution by certain territorial units of the settlement, departmental affiliation, functional nature of buildings.

The main task of qualitative accounting of buildings and structures is to give a quality description of the objects in terms of building materials, capital, material and spiritual obsolescence of buildings and structures.

In the quality accounting of buildings and structures, taking into account the characteristics of the grouping of buildings as a key indicator, depending on the purpose, they can be classified into the following categories:

- Category "A". Buildings and structures used by the owner to conduct business, they are divided into the following classes:
 - Specialized buildings and structures (eg. oil refineries, chemical plants, workshops for machinery and equipment) that are adapted to run a particular type of business and are usually sold in conjunction with that business;
 - Non-specialized buildings - shops, offices, factories, warehouses, usually they are sold or rented.
- Category "B". Buildings and structures for investment are owned primarily for the purpose of generating income on a lease basis or for profit from invested capital.
- Category "V". Excess buildings and structures are no longer needed to run a business today or in the future, and therefore can be called redundant real estate.

The computer database is formed on the basis of a single system of state-registered data of buildings and structures and the classification, which is based on the division of groups of objects on the following characteristics: buildings and structures are described in terms of purpose, property rights or other material rights, as well as in terms of construction, technical characteristics, territoriality, belonging to legal entities and individuals.

Taking into account the characteristics of these classes, it is expedient to use the data of the classifier of buildings and structures in the creation and maintenance of accounts of buildings and structures and their harmonization, in which buildings and structures are described as follows [2]:

- residential buildings;
- non-residential buildings;
- III facilities;
- historical and cultural monuments.

When summarizing and systematizing computer data on buildings and structures, it is advisable to create a quantitative and qualitative accounting of the above-mentioned buildings and structures on the basis of the following indicators: legal, technical and economic indicators for the creation of the state cadastre of buildings and structures:

- belonging to the economic complex;
- by duty;
- by type of law;
- by form of ownership;
- by economic indicators;
- by the constructive structure;
- level of earthquake resistance;
- construction description;
- engineering support;
- by types of protection;

The systematization and accounting of buildings can be summarized as follows (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Building accounting system.

Using the information of the proposed classifier of buildings and structures (II-non-residential buildings; III-buildings; IV-historical and cultural monuments) in the creation and maintenance of the account of buildings and structures and their unification, in the future will create opportunities for positive solutions to the following issues:

- Generalization and systematization of cadastral data on district, city buildings and structures as of the quarter and December 31 of the year and submission to the National Geographic Information System of the Republic of Uzbekistan aimed at a single system of state cadastres and integration of state cadastres;
- creation of a collection of modern and historical geoinformation of buildings and structures of the district, city geofund warehouse;
- Further deepening of market relations of buildings and structures in the country, including tax, rent, insurance, investment and business development, provision of fast and quality services [3];

- creation of organizational and legal aspects of compliance with the rules of urban planning, engineering and construction, as well as the integrated economic development of the regions on a scientific basis for the efficient and rational use of buildings and structures, etc.

The complexity of the information system is the need to collect a variety of reliable information about buildings and structures throughout the country, the need to constantly update, store and provide information to consumers in a timely manner. The complexity of the system, in turn, requires the study of information in terms of quantitative and qualitative descriptions of buildings and structures attached to the subjects using buildings and structures, as well as to determine the practical and economic significance of the information.

This system has a number of features, they are:

- complexity of cadastral indicators;
- presentation of information in various forms;
- the need to digitize the system.

A necessary condition for the functioning of the system is the organic connection of cadastral processes. The interconnection between systems requires information and its development. The development of information requires its delivery to the consumer. Therefore, this or that system cannot be superior to each other. They form a single, organically linked material-abstract system of cadastre.

CONCLUSION

Systematization and accounting of buildings and structures requires a systematic approach to this process in the information supply. In this regard, it is recommended to follow the proposed system in improving the components of the cadastre and the corresponding processes and information supply. According to the author's recommendation, it is necessary to pay special attention to the provision of information to consumers in a timely manner on the basis of systematization, analysis and registration of cadastral information in the system.

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1989-1995 - Junior Research Fellow at Samarkand State Institute of Architecture and Construction, Assistant Professor, Department of Engineering Geodesy, Deputy Dean of the Faculty of Construction Technology

1995-1996 - Dean of the Faculty of Construction Technology, Samarkand State Institute of Architecture and Construction

1996-1997 - Acting Head of the Real Estate Cadastre Service of Samarkand Region

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2006-2008 - Head of the Department of Land Resources and State Cadastre of Samarkand region

2008-2010 - Deputy Head of the State Unitary Enterprise "Ermulkkadastrxizmati" Samarkand region, State Registrar

2010-2018 - Head of the Department of Geodesy, Cartography and Cadastre of Samarkand State Institute of Architecture and Construction

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